

This is the crystal absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If the crystal is seated, therefore the crystal stands, however, if the crystal stands, therefore the crystal is seated. And so the outcome of that paradox is that the crystal stands. However, if the crystal stands, therefore the crystal is seated, however, if the crystal is seated, therefore the crystal stands. And so the outcome of that paradox is that the crystal is seated. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that the crystal either stands or is seated.

This set is timed as 21:32, and is dated as the 9th day of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.